

1. Development of leaf BI in different treatments until crop maturity, Almora, India.

2. Percentage of leaf and neck BI and yield levels under different fungicide treatments, Almora, India

Occurrence of sheath blotch (SBI) in India

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SBI, caused by *Pyrenochaeta oryzae* Miyake, is common at light to moderate severity in Ambala, Kurukshetra, Karnal, Sonapat, and Jind districts. In trials at RRS Kaul during 1979 kharif, SBI appeared between maximum tillering and booting on sheaths just below the ligules as a brown spot surrounded by water-soaked areas. Spots bleached in the middle, became milky white, and were studded with numerous black pycnidia (Fig. 1).

Damage varied with variety. On Jaya, symptoms were limited to the sheaths just below the ligules. On Pusa 2-21, the fungus penetrated deep into sheaths and damaged the culm, causing it to break. At RRS Kaul, the disease reduced panicle emergence in late lines PAU 35-5-32 and RP6-56-516 because the base of the flag leaf sheath rotted (Fig. 2).

The pathogen isolated from diseased tissues did not produce pycnidia on PDA, paddy grains, or typha leaves. Three varieties were inoculated at two growth stages: at maximum tillering stage by inserting a rice grain culture or typha leaf-

1. Blotch on sheath with a white center studded with black pycnidia. Note the spot on the junctura and leaf sheath.

2. Flag leaf sheath showing SBI with pycnidia and a partially emerged panicle and unfilled grain.

piece culture between sheath and culm or spraying the three upper leaves with a mycelial suspension, and at booting by inserting a rice grain culture in the boot or spraying the three upper leaves with mycelial suspension.

SBI symptoms developed from all inoculation methods. Brown spots appeared on leaf sheaths 3 d after inocula-

tion. Alternating brown and yellow bands developed on the leaves. Pycnidia formed only on the leaf sheaths. Later tests showed that resistant, intermediate, and susceptible varieties could be identified by inserting typha leaf-piece culture at maximum tillering stage and observing the reaction. □

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A quantitative method for assessing virulence of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola*

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Bacterial leaf streak (BLS) caused by *X. c.* pv. *oryzicola* is an important rice disease in tropical Asia. Symptoms are narrow, translucent streaks between the leaf veins and bacterial ooze.

In a preliminary study, susceptible lesions induced by some isolates produced more bacterial ooze, suggesting the possible relation of ooze production and isolate virulence in the host-parasite interaction.

We assessed the virulence of isolates BLS37, BLS93, and BLS102 on resistant IR58 and susceptible IR14753-120-3 using the following parameters:

- incubation period, the time interval between inoculation and visible symptoms;
- latent period, the time from inoculation to first ooze production;

Ooze production of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola* isolates in resistant IR58 and susceptible IR14753-120-3 rice varieties 15 d after inoculation.

- ooze production, ooze produced per 30 cm² leaf surface; and
- lesion length, measured in millimeters.

Inoculated plants were kept in the greenhouse and visible infection and ooze production were monitored daily. The ooze was carefully isolated by scraping the lesion surface with camel-hair brush 15 d after inoculation and immediately placed in a test tube containing 5 ml of peptone sucrose broth. Tenfold series of dilution were made and 0.1 ml suspension was plated on PSA medium. Colonies were counted 3 d later.

Irrespective of rice cultivar, isolate BLS93 had shorter incubation period and latent period (see table), higher ooze pro-

Mean incubation period and latent period for 3 *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola* isolates on 2 rice cultivars, IRRI.

Variety	Isolate	Incubation period (d)	Ooze observed (d) after incubation	Latent period ^a (d)
IR58	BLS93	6.5	2.5	9.0
	BLS102	7.0	2.0	9.0
	BLS37	8.0	2.0	10
IR14753-120-3	BLS93	5.0	3.0	8.0
	BLS102	6.0	2.0	8.0
	BLS37	8.0	2.0	10

^aIncubation period + days when ooze was observed after incubation period.